

Supporting Information

How much platinum is enough? Stability of Pt-coated titanium films for porous transport layers (PTLs) in acidic and fluoride-containing electrolyte

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Thickness calibration

The Pt and Ti layer thicknesses were calibrated using atomic force microscopy (AFM), as illustrated in the figure below. AFM measurements were conducted using a MultiMode 8 AFM (Bruker) in tapping mode. SCANASYST-AIR probes (Bruker) with a nominal tip radius of 2 nm were used. Image processing was carried out using the Gwyddion software.

Before deposition, a small droplet of varnish was applied to the Si substrate to act as a mask. After deposition, the varnish was removed, leaving a well-defined, sharp step between the masked and unmasked regions (Figure a). AFM measurements were then performed by scanning the tip perpendicular to this step, and the resulting height profile provided the film thickness (Figure b-d). Owing to the very high vertical resolution of AFM (on the order of 0.1 nm), the uncertainty in the thickness determination is considered negligible.

After determining the deposition rate (layer thickness per deposition time), the thickness of the Pt layers used in this study was controlled by precisely adjusting the deposition time.

The thickness of the Ti layer was initially calibrated. Titanium was deposited for 10 min, yielding a thickness of 97.6 ± 2 nm, as determined by AFM (see image below). The uncertainty here corresponds to the surface roughness (R_a - mean roughness), which was estimated from the corresponding AFM image to be approximately 2 nm. This thickness is in good agreement with the intended value of 100 nm.

The Pt deposition was calibrated separately. Pt was first deposited for 4 min, resulting in a layer thickness of 80.7 ± 2 nm as determined by AFM (see image below).

To adjust the Pt thickness, a target value of 30 nm was selected, and the subsequent layer was deposited for 1 min 30 s. This deposition was performed on top of the Ti layer to verify the total thickness of the Pt/Ti system. The AFM-determined thickness was 127.8 ± 3 nm (see image below), which corresponds well to the intended 100 nm (97.6 ± 2 nm) for Ti and 30 nm (30.2 ± 1 nm) for Pt, within a small experimental error.

All other Pt thicknesses were then adjusted in the same way by precisely varying the deposition time.

Fig. S1 - Cyclic voltammograms of the Pt(1 nm) and Pt(100 nm)/Ti film recorded at the beginning of test (BOT) and end of test (EOT), at 10 mV s⁻¹ in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ HClO₄ electrolyte.

Protocol I

Fig. S2 – Titanium dissolution profiles for the 1, 5, and 50 nm Pt/Ti films during the CV protocol.

Protocol II

Fig. S3 – Titanium dissolution profiles for the 1, 3, 5, and 10 nm Pt/Ti films during the current pulses protocol.

Fig. S4 – Titanium and platinum dissolution amounts during (a) protocol I and (b) protocol II.

Fig. S5 - Cyclic voltammograms of the Ti film recorded at the beginning of test (BOT) and end of test (EOT), at 10 mV s^{-1} in (a) $0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ HClO}_4$ and (b) $0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ HClO}_4 + 0.1 \text{ mmol L}^{-1} \text{ KF}$ electrolyte.

Fig. S6 – Magnified view of the titanium dissolution profile for the Pt (20 nm)/Ti film corresponding to Fig. 6 in the main text.